

JUSTICE - 2030: UZBEKISTAN ON THE PATH TO MODERNIZATION OF THE JUSTICE SYSTEM

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Abstract

This article analyzes the directions of modernizing the justice system within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, reforms aimed at improving the judicial and legal system, digitalization, and protection of human rights are examined. The article reviews the existing legal framework and proposes suggestions for the future development of the "Justice 2030" strategy.

Keywords

Justice system, judicial reform, digitalization, artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence in legal services, digital technologies, legal technologies (legal tech), automation of legal services, digitalization of legal services, use of artificial intelligence in legal services.

Introduction

The "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. DP-158, marked the beginning of a new stage in the country's development. This strategy includes five priority areas and one hundred important goals, through the implementation of which deep reforms in the social, economic, and political spheres of Uzbekistan are expected.

"We have adopted the Development Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030." This strategy aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, and we are fully and steadfastly fulfilling all our commitments" [1]

One of the important directions of the strategy is aimed at modernizing the justice system. In this direction, measures are planned to improve the judicial and legal system, digitalization, protection of human rights, and the use of artificial intelligence and big data technologies. In particular, it is planned to reliably protect the rights and freedoms of citizens through the development of the administrative justice system, strengthening judicial control, and deepening judicial reforms.

This article analyzes the directions of modernization of the justice system within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy. In particular, the ongoing reforms to improve the judicial and legal system, digitalization, and protection of human rights will be considered. The article analyzes the existing

legislative framework and puts forward proposals for the development of the future justice system ("Justice 2030").

Directions of modernization of the justice system

The "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. DP-158, aims to bring legal reforms in the country to a new level. One of the 4 priority areas of the Strategy is ensuring the rule of law, organizing public administration at the service of the people.

Modernization of the justice system in this area includes the following important tasks:

Goal 85 of the Decree: "Establishing effective judicial control over the activities of state bodies and officials and further development of the administrative justice system."

Based on this norm, it is planned to ensure the independence of administrative courts and improve the mechanisms for considering citizens' claims against state bodies. This expands the possibilities of real protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens.

The Strategy defines goal 85: "Increasing the effectiveness of dispute resolution at the pre-trial stage by 50 percent."

This goal provides for the development of mechanisms for pre-trial dispute resolution - mediation, arbitration, the ombudsman institution, and other forms of legal assistance. This is aimed at reducing the overload of the justice system and offering affordable and prompt legal solutions. Goal 86 of the Decree: "Increasing the level of access to justice by strengthening the independence of the judiciary and ensuring transparency in its activities."

Public announcement of court decisions, open court sessions, strengthening the system of accountability of judges - all this serves to gain the trust of citizens in the justice system. Goal 86 of the Strategy: "Full implementation of the principle of judicial self-government in the management of the judicial system and full formation of a system of bodies of the judicial community."

Guarantees are being created for the legal strengthening of the material security, independence, and freedom of judges from political and administrative pressure. Goal 87 of the Strategy: "Directing the activities of law enforcement agencies to protect the interests, dignity, and rights of the individual."

Based on the "single window" principle, electronic public services (for example, legal information, application submission, obtaining a permit) are

being widely implemented. The digitalization of these services creates convenient, unbureaucratic approaches for the population.

The tasks defined within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy are aimed at bringing the justice system closer to the interests of the people, effectively protecting human rights, and ensuring justice and the rule of law. Decree No.DP-158 defines specific criteria and deadlines for these areas, which is a document of strategic, practical, and legal significance.

Directions of digitalization of the justice system and the introduction of modern technologies

The "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy defines digital transformation as a tool for fundamental reforms in public administration and the legal sphere. Goal 77 of the Presidential Decree specifically emphasizes improving the justice system based on advanced technologies:

"Implementation of the "Service State" system for the population by expanding the scope of digitalization of public services, elimination of bureaucratic procedures in relations between the citizen and the state."

Today, the Ministry of Justice has launched electronic services through the "Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services" (my.gov.uz) to provide legal assistance to citizens. In addition, citizens are increasing their legal literacy through the portal "Legal Information," the National Database of Legislation of Uzbekistan on the Internet (lex.uz).

In order to further develop this area, the following proposals will be put forward, and by 2030 these services will be:

- ✓ receiving legal consultations online,
- ✓ conclusion of electronic contracts,
- ✓ Automatic document analysis.
- ✓ expansion with legal monitoring services.

This, in turn, saves time and costs, and increases the legal literacy of citizens.

If we take digital legal services as an example, for example, the "E-huquqshunos" system increased efficiency by automating the processes of preparing, analyzing legal documents, and providing legal advice. Legislative violations were prevented. These systems serve to ensure the promptness and accuracy of legal services.

However, these systems cannot completely replace the human factor. For example, in such tasks as contextual analysis of documents, the solution of complex legal issues, the experience of human legal specialists is necessary.

Additionally, technical malfunctions or inaccurate data can lead to system errors.

Possibilities of using artificial intelligence

The introduction of AI (artificial intelligence) technologies can serve to automate legal services. For example,

- ✓ automatic analysis of contracts,
- ✓ systems for analyzing judicial practice,
- ✓ AI monitoring of the activities of judges and lawyers,
- ✓ forecasting of legal risks.

"Despite the obvious possibilities, artificial intelligence does not solve systemic problems in the government and, if not implemented thoughtfully and strategically, can exacerbate problems related to service provision, privacy, and ethics. Agencies interested in implementing artificial intelligence can learn from the government's previous transformation efforts, as well as from the implementation of artificial intelligence in the private sector. Government agencies should consider the following six strategies for the application of artificial intelligence in their work: • make artificial intelligence part of a goal-oriented, citizen-oriented program"[2]

Artificial intelligence (AI) is used in judicial practice as an auxiliary tool, for example, in tasks such as automatic document analysis, forecasting court decisions. For example, in Canada, the Toronto-based startup Blue J Legal launched a new artificial intelligence software that helps predict how courts will resolve labor law issues. [3] However, AI does not take into account human emotions, moral norms, and contextual details when making decisions. Therefore, AI should be only an auxiliary tool in making court decisions, and the main decision should be made by a human judge.

Conclusion

Normative legal acts on the introduction of modern technologies into legislation serve as a legal basis for the modernization of the justice system, strengthening the protection of human rights and ensuring equal access of citizens to legal services. In particular, the "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy is the main concept uniting all reforms in this area.

Proposals for the Development of the Future Justice System ("Justice 2030") according to the "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy, approved by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-158

Expansion of the range and improvement of the quality of legal services;

Current reforms in the digitalization of the justice system contribute to increasing the openness, speed, and transparency of public services. Platforms like Lex.ai prove this in practice.

Although the introduction of artificial intelligence provides automation in legal matters, it is strictly foreseen that it will not lead to the loss of the human factor.

Firstly, standardization of legal technologies:

It is necessary to develop national technical standards and a code of ethics for artificial intelligence, chatbots, and digital systems used in the justice system.

Secondly, labor guarantees and AI balance:

To legally mandate retraining programs so that the number of employees does not decrease as a result of the introduction of artificial intelligence.

Thirdly, creation of a solid legal framework in the field of Big Data:

Creation of a consistent procedure and monitoring system for the processing, export-import, and use of personal data.

Fourthly, implementation of mobile platforms of legal services on a gratuitous basis:

Fifthly, legal chatbots (e.g., Lex.ai) should be provided free of charge or in a subsidized form, especially for vulnerable groups.

Sixthly, leaving court decisions with the participation of artificial intelligence under human control:

AI decisions should be only advisory in nature, and the main word should be spoken by a person - a judge.

"Justice - 2030" is not only a project for the digitalization of the legal system, but also a systemic movement aimed at strengthening citizens' trust in justice and transforming the judicial system into an institution serving the interests of the people. The main task on this path is to harmonize technology with the principles of human rights and justice.

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